

Irish Research eLibrary

National Open Access Monitor Survey: Cost to Sector Survey

Introduction

This survey is carried out by [IReL](#) at [Maynooth University](#), as part of the the [National Open Access Monitor project](#), funded by Ireland's [National Open Research Forum \(NORF\)](#) under the NORF Open Research Fund 2022.

The purpose of this survey is to capture the costs for stakeholders (resource allocation, systems etc) to contribute to the National Open Access Monitor project. This is to enable an analysis of the overall cost of this project to the national research system. Contributions will be pseudonymised to the high-level stakeholder group.

We request that each organisation/entity/group provides only one submission to this survey.

This survey will open for general submissions in September/October 2024.

If your organisation/entity/group withdraws from participating in the project in advance of that date, please complete this survey at the time of withdrawal, to capture the costs for your organisation/entity/group to contribute to that point.

If you have any questions, please contact Dr Catherine Ferris (National Open Access Monitor, Project Manager) catherine.ferris@mu.ie

Please note: all survey data will be retained and hosted on a third party (Online Surveys) server and not on a MU server. For more information on how and why this survey data is being collected, and how it will be managed, please refer to the [Stakeholder Information Sheet and Consent Form](#).

Consent Required

Please confirm that you have completed the Consent Form [\[link\]](#) and returned it to catherine.ferris@mu.ie before beginning this survey.

Please note: if the date/time of the survey response precedes the date/time that the consent form is received, the survey response will be **immediately deleted**. * *Required*

yes

no

Identification

Your name * *Required*

Your job title * *Required*

Your email address (the Project Manager may need to follow-up with you on your responses. Your email address will not be made public.) * *Required*

Please enter a valid email address.

The name of the organisation, group or entity that you represent * *Required*

Survey responses will be pseudonymised to the high-level stakeholder group.

Please indicate how best to categorise your organisation/entity/group, for this purpose.
* *Required*

Government

- Research performing organisation
- Research funding organisation
- Publisher
- Service provider (including research infrastructure)
- Research group
- Individual contributor
- Other

Cost Submission

Please indicate the cost to your organisation/entity/group of contributing to the National Open Access Monitor project, for the period 16th December 2022 to 31 October 2024.

Submissions are to include the value (in Euro) of resource allocation and systems, including in-kind contributions.

Each organisation/entity/group may calculate the cost of their contribution in line with their specific circumstances. In general, resourcing should be calculated at X number of hours at Y paygrade. Any infrastructural costs should include those outlaid to purchase, maintain and resource.

Only costs which resulted as consequence of the National Open Access Monitor project should be included. * *Required*

Please enter a whole number (integer).

Submit Survey

Please click "Finish" below to submit this survey.

Confirmation

The survey is complete. Thank you for contributing.
